

Effect of Using the Competitive Learning Method in Improving the Skill Performance of Certain Handball Skills among the Hashemite University Students

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: December 08, 2020</p> <p>Accepted: February 03, 2021</p> <p>Keywords : Competitive Learning Method, Skill Performance, Handball</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4499174</p>	<p><i>This study aimed at identifying the effect of the competitive learning method in improving the skill performance of both the pass and catch skills, in handball among the faculty of physical education and sport sciencestudents in the Hashemite University, during the second semester of the academic year 2017/2018. The sample consisted of (30) male students of the handball course, who were distributed over two equal groups. The first, the experimental group, were taught using the competitive method, and the second, the control, were taught using the traditional method. The handball curriculum was taught in addition to the application of proposed exercises of the pass and catch skills. The means, standard deviations, and T-test results were calculated to define the differences among the groups. The results showed that the competitive learning method group students overperformed those of the traditional group in both skills. The results further showed that the competitive learning method has an effective impact in developing the pass and catch skills. The researcher recommended the need to diversify the use of the learning methods in all sports.</i></p>

Introduction

Learning methods are of the core components of the educational curriculum (Aljawarneh & Atan, 2018). In this concern, the educational objectives cannot be evaluated in the educational curriculum, which the professionals select, without the teacher in the academic classroom lessons, through the methods he/she uses in the teaching process, or through the trainer inside the playground (Aljawarneh et al., 2020). Motor learning in the sports training is the process of transferring the information from the coach to the player (Alsafadi et al., 2020). The changes that take place in the motor behavior result from the training or educational process that aim at developing the player's performance (Alshare et al., 2020). The competitive learning method is among the modern methods that were brought by the educational movement (Mahafzah et al., 2020). It means the competition of the learners among themselves to achieve a predetermined educational objective, which is the winning of the taught group (Alomari et al., 2020). This style had proven successful in stimulating the learner's desire and urging him/her to exert the maximum possible effort. This competition may be by another learner or by the same learner with him/herself (Al-Dulaimi, 2013).

The learning process consists of many basic components (teacher, student, curriculum and educational environment) (Al-Omari et al., 2020). It is a continuous series of relationships that arise between the teacher and student, and is deemed a link between the teacher and student where the students' tendencies and needs are taken into account (Oudat, 2012).

Handball is one of the most collectively practiced games in the world, despite the fact it was not included in the Olympic Games until 1972. Nonetheless, it gained its status and publicity at the world level (Aljawarneh & Al-Omari, 2018). The game includes many individual basic skills, such as holding the ball, passing, catching, bouncing, shooting and deception processes, as well as certain skills used in the attack and defense processes. Mastery of all the skills depends on the player's physical fitness level (Showkeh, 2013).

Learning any sport game skill requires the use of modern scientific methods and styles, which should be used without causing boredom in the learners (Al-Da'abseh, et al., 2018). The competition element should be used in teaching to create a stimulation climate and increase their motility to learn (Mahjoub, 2002). The use of the competitive learning method in learning the basic skills increases the learners' motivation, and provides the learner experiences that are strongly related to the practical reality more than any other teaching method. In addition, the competitive method has an effective and positive effect on the development of the skill performance (Zghair, 2013; Al-Fartousi, 2005).

Handball is among the collective games that enjoyed wide spread with its audiences and fans, because of its fun, artful profiles and sports performance that needs physical strength (Al-Da'abseh, et al., 2018). Thus, the significance of this study is embedded in providing the game teachers and learners with a scientific support,

with the pass and catch skills are of the most important skills in learning the game. Therefore, focus and attention should be placed on teaching these two skills in order to learn other skills.

Study Problem

Pass and catch skills are among the basic skills to learn the handball game, as by learning these skills the player can control directing the ball anywhere to the location of his/her colleagues inside the playground. Furthermore, the ball catching skill signifies how far the player has a control on the ball and avoidance of its falling from his/her hand. Accordingly, the learners' development level depends on their mastery level of the pass and catch skills. Through the researchers' work in education and handball teaching, and the revision of a number of research works and studies, such as Showkeh (2013) and Zghair (2013), they found a clear difficulty among the novice learners on the performance of the pass and catch skills. The player does not perceive the importance of passing the ball to his/her colleagues and how it should be passed to the appropriate player very accurately and smoothly in the playground. Based on the above, the researcher decided to introduce the competitive learning method to assist the students in a factual learning of both the pass and catch skills.

Study Objective

The study aimed to identify the effect of the competitive learning method in improving the skill performance of both the pass and catch skills in handball among the students of the faculty of physical education and sports science, who are studying the handball course in the Hashemite University.

Study Questions

- 1- Are there statistically significant differences at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) level between the pre and post measurements in the control group skill performance level?
- 2- Are there statistically significant differences at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) level between the pre and post measurements in the experimental group skill performance level?
- 3- Are there statistically significant differences at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) level between the post measurements of both the control and experimental groups' skill performance level?

Methods

Study design

The researchers applied the experimental method for both the control and experimental groups, as it fits the nature and objective of the study.

Population and Sample

The study population comprised (36) male students of the faculty of physical education and sport science in the Hashemite University, during the 2nd semester of the academic year 2017/2018, who are enrolled for the handball course. The sample consisted of (30) students who were distributed over two equal groups: control group and experimental group. The control group students were taught using the traditional method, while the experimental group students were taught using the competitive learning method. The researcher took the premeasurements of the (weight, height, age, and both the pass and catch tests in handball) variables for both groups. T-test was also applied to ensure the groups' parity, as shown in Table (1).

Table (1). Means (M's), Standard Deviations (SDs), T Value and Significance Level of the Weight, Height, Age and Pass and Catch Tests among the Participants of the Two Groups.

Variables	Measurement Unit	Control Group		Experimental Group		T	Sign
		M	SD	M	SD		
Weight	Kg.	71.40	3.55	71.70	3.50	0.28	0.77
Height	Cm.	172.70	3.90	162/60	4.40	-1.08	0.27
Age	Year	18.72	0.70	18.70	0.66	0.24	0.80
Pass and catch Test	No. of Pass and catch Times	22.55	1.20	22.50	1.20	0.29	0.78

Table (1) shows that p- value for the variables more than ($\alpha \leq 0.05$), which implies the parity of the two groups in the pretest in the study variables.

Tools and Instruments

The researcher employed many tools (medical scale to measure the weight, measuring tape to measure the height, whistle, handballs, and tests to measure the ball pass and catch, and data registration form).

Scientific coefficient of the Tests

The study instrument validity was verified through its content validity by presenting the tests to six professionals in handball learning and physical education teaching methods in the physical education colleges of four Jordanian universities (the Hashemite University, University of Jordan, Al-Yarmouk University, and Mutah University), who appreciated its validity. The reliability was further assured using the test-pretest procedures and calculating Pearson Correlation Coefficient, and Cronbach coefficient, which yielded (0.88) reliability coefficient value.

Study Application

The study was applied over a 4-week period at the rate of (3) educational units per week for each group, and (50) minutes were allocated for every unit. The researchers took the measurements of the students who attended the educational units (n=30), and the post-measurements were then taken for both groups.

Statistical Processing

The means, standard deviations and T-test were calculated using the SPSS program.

Results and discussion of the first question: "Are there statistically significant differences at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) level between the pre and post measurements in the control group skill performance level?" To answer this question, the researchers calculated the M's, SDs and T-test as illustrated in Table (2).

Table (2). M's, SDs and T-test between the Pre and Post Measurements of the Control Group for the Pass and catch Skills

Variables	Measurement Unit	Pre-Measurement		Post-Measurement		T	Sign
		M	SD	M	SD		
Pass and catch Test	No. of Times	22.55	1.20	26.04	1.28	13.020	0.001

Table (2) shows statistically significant differences between the post and pre measurements of the control group, in favor of the post measurement. The researchers ascribe this result to that the lecturer's explanation and providing the model led to an improvement in the students' performance. This result is in line with the study of Oudat (2016), which confirmed that the teaching method offers the student ample opportunity to exchange experiences with the teacher individually about the skills the student performs. It also gives the teacher a sufficient opportunity to provide the students with feedback during the practical application.

Results and discussion of the second question: "Are there statistically significant differences at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) level between the pre and post measurements in the experimental group skill performance level?" To answer this question, the researchers calculated the M's SDs and T-test as illustrated in Table (3).

Table (3). M's, SDs and T-test between the Pre and Post Measurements of the Experimental Group for the Pass and catch Skills

Variables	Measurement Unit	Pre-Measurement		Post-Measurement		T	Sign
		M	SD	M	SD		
Pass and catch Test	No. of Times	22.50	1.20	28.60	1.59	25.24	0.001

Table (3) indicates the presence of statistically significant differences between the pre and post measurements of the experimental group, in favor of the post-measurement. The researchers attribute this result to that the competitive method leads to an improvement and development in the handball pass and catch skills, and gives the student longer application time. This result is in agreement with Khasawneh, et al (2011) in that the use of the competitive teaching method leads to a better utilization of the application time. Consequently, it leads to the improvement and mastery of both the skill and digital performances.

Results and discussion of the third question: "Are there statistically significant differences at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) level between the post measurements of both the control and experimental groups' skill performance level?" To answer this question, the researchers calculated the M's SDs and T-test as shown in Table (4).

Table (4). M's, SDs and T-test between the Post Measurements of the Control and Experimental Groups for the Pass and catch Skills

Variables	Measurement Unit	Control Group		Experimental Group		T	Sign
		M	SD	M	SD		
Pass and catch Test	No. of Times	26.04	1.28	28.60	1.59	5.44	0.001

Table (4) shows statistically significant differences between the two groups in the post measurement of the pass and catch skills, in favor of the experimental groups. The researchers impute this result to the fact that the competitive method added privacy to the performance, as it works toward performing the pass and catch skills during both playing and competition, which, in turn, led to the development of the motor functions to a higher level than the traditional method. In this concern, the researchers are in line with Al-Fartousi (2005) in that the performance development and improvement essentially depend on the skill recurrence and number of failure and success times. As a result, the player will achieve the highest harmony level, through which he will successfully perform the skill in a manner that is consistent with its objective, within the actual competition framework inside the playground.

Conclusions

Based on the above discussion and analysis, the researcher approached the following conclusions:

- 1- The competitive method effectively affected the improvement and development of the handball pass and catch skills.
- 2- Performing the pass and catch skills within the play and competition periods produces speedy learning, time curtailment and performance accuracy.

Recommendations

The researcher offered the following recommendations:

- 1- The need to diversify the learning methods of the motor skills in all the sports games.
- 2- The need to use the competitive learning method, as it proved positive effectiveness in the improvement and development of the pass and catch skills in handball.
- 3- Carrying out similar studies using different methods, such as brain training, and use of electronic devices, such as photography, TV and internet to teach handball skills.

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